

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab Evaluation Plan

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Introduction

Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIL)

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIL, www.esil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, diverse teams through the ESIL Network. ESIL follows a broad set of values (Table 1) that guide the center's development and operation. ESIL brings together a diverse community of environmental and biological data scientists to turn environmental and biological data into actionable understanding and knowledge toward a more sustainable society. The center activities are organized into four broad pillars (Fig. 1) that are supporting ESIL's mission: "Empower an inclusive and diverse community to accelerate continental-scale environmental data science (EDS)".

This center accelerates discovery in environmental data science through six broad activities:

- i. promoting a diversity of perspectives and inclusion
- ii. developing data tools and cyberinfrastructure to study the Earth and combine existing data
- iii. leveraging cutting-edge data analytics for environmental and biological sciences
- iv. educating a diverse research community
- v. broadening use of Earth data science open education portal
- vi. creating a community that enables team science and facilitates inclusive access to scalable computing.

Table 1. ESIL VALUES

Inclusive	Diversity
Innovation	Open Access
Transparency	Resilience
Collaboration	Culturally-sensitive
Respect	Transformative
Sustainability	

Figure 1. Four Pillars of ESIL.

Evaluation Purpose

Evaluation activities for the ESIL Data Center outlined in this evaluation plan will contribute to and support the dynamic and iterative development and improvement of the synthesis center, the ESIL community and all ESIL activities. The evaluation team will conduct evaluation activities in collaboration with the **ESIL leadership team** and coordinate with the **Team Science** and the **ESIL diversity, equity and inclusion teams**, encouraging reflection and collaborative engagement throughout the development and implementation of the center. Evaluation findings will be shared regularly with the leadership team along with recommendations for iterative improvements. Reports will summarize the findings and allow for reporting to the **National Science Foundation** and the **community**. The ESIL evaluation will include data and artifacts collection that includes human subjects research and evaluation methodologies; all evaluation data that may result in generalizable findings will be covered under Institutional Review Board oversight.

Evaluation Frameworks

The evaluation will be guided by three evaluation frameworks. The overarching evaluation approach will be grounded in *Collaborative Evaluation* (King & Stevahn 2013; Shulha et al. 2016). The evaluation of all program components, activities and outcomes will utilize the *Context, Input, Process and Product Evaluation model* (Stufflebeam, 2003; Mertens & Wilson, 2012; Fitzpatrick et al., 2011; Zang et al., 2011). The ESIL education programs will be evaluated using *Guskey's Evaluation model* for professional training (Hanover Research, 2014; Guskey et al., 2014).

COLLABORATIVE EVALUATION

The overall evaluation approach will be grounded in principles of collaborative evaluation (King & Stevahn 2013; Shulha et al. 2016), a culturally-responsive framework used in partnerships with multiple partners. Collaborative evaluation is guided by eight principles (Fig. 2); each of these principles needs to be included in the evaluation to ensure effective implementation. However, the extent to which each principle is emphasized and prioritized depends on the context of the work (Shulha et al., 2016). For the evaluation within the ESIL synthesis center, a collaborative evaluation approach will be utilized for the work with the project leadership team, project partners, and the advisory board. Below, we briefly describe how each principle will be taken into consideration.

Figure 2. Integrated principles that guide the collaborative evaluation approach (from Shulha et al., 2016).

Collaborative Evaluation Principles as implemented in ESIIIL

Clarify Motivation for Collaboration: The evaluation team will apply a participatory evaluation approach and take part in ESIIIL leadership meetings, trainings and retreats. The evaluation team will continually work with ESIIIL leadership to ensure that the evaluation aligns with the goals and activities of the center, engage in discussion and feedback sessions and share reports that outline proposed evaluation activities and summarize evaluation findings from periodic team reflection meetings with the leadership team and advisory board. Iterative revisions will be made to the evaluation plan, the goals and the data collection and analysis plan based on the iterative discussions.

Develop a Shared Understanding of the Program: The evaluation team will continually work with ESIIIL leadership to reflect on the goals of the center, map activities against goals and objectives, and initiate regular review of this shared understanding to ensure that the evaluation aligns with the goals and activities of the center.

Foster Meaningful Relationships: The evaluation team will engage in regular communication with ESIIIL Leadership members, attending meetings and engaging in discussions around the development of the center and the implementation of activities. The evaluation team will practice deep listening to gain an understanding of leadership and partner perspectives to incorporate feedback into evaluation activities and the information reported back to the team. The evaluators will work closely with the ESIIIL Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion team and the Indigenous Community lead to build cultural competence and prioritize an inclusive and respectful collaborative evaluation process. Evaluation activities will be responsive to center and team needs.

Promote Appropriate Participatory Processes: The evaluation team will engage with ESIIIL leadership to align center goals with evaluation activities and to develop the evaluation tools to ensure that data collected appropriately address team members' questions about successes and improvements made toward meeting ESIIIL goals. Center goals and evaluation questions will be reviewed and revised in partnership with the leadership team and regularly revisited. Final decisions on the evaluation plan and instruments will be made by the evaluation team, with ongoing discussion and input from the leadership team.

Monitor and Respond to Resource Availability: The evaluators will strive to make collaborative evaluation discussions part of regular team meetings and will be open to discussion around ESIIIL leadership team's and ESIIIL partners' time allocations as they engage in collaborative evaluation. This will be addressed during regular check-ins to gather feedback from the leadership team and advisory board.

Monitor Evaluation Progress and Quality: Regular reflection with the ESIIIL leadership team and advisory board will enable the evaluators to adjust the evaluation activities as needed to respond to changes in the evaluation context (e.g., people, activities, programs, information needs, and process needs).

Promote Evaluative Thinking: The evaluation team will work with ESIIIL team members to identify ways to use the evaluation data for group learning and the improvement of processes and activities. The evaluation team will be open to feedback to improve evaluation processes and communication.

Follow Through to Realize Use: The evaluation team will present data to the ESIIIL leadership team in a way that allows for reflection, discussion, and co-creation of knowledge. The evaluators will encourage use of the data to engage in the continual improvement of the center and for both the evaluation and leadership teams' processes.

CONTEXT, INPUT, PROCESS and PRODUCT (CIPP) EVALUATION MODEL

The Context, Input, Process and Product (CIPP) evaluation model is a popular and well-established decision- and management-oriented program evaluation framework for programs, projects, or institutions that guides the systematic collection of data about strengths and limitations. The CIPP evaluation model allows and facilitates iterative improvements and measurement of outcomes (Stufflebeam, 2003; Mertens & Wilson, 2012; Fitzpatrick et al., 2011; Zang et al., 2011). The four phases of evaluation will be applied to ESIL with the following approach (Fig. 3):

Context Evaluation: Context evaluation paints the big picture of the context, ecosystem and setting in which ESIL is situated/being established. ESIL's context evaluation will focus on the assessment of the resources and the background of the synthesis center. During the context evaluation, the evaluators will revise the goals and objectives of the center, draft evaluation questions in partnership with the ESIL leadership team and define the scope of the evaluation. The context evaluation also includes the development of an understanding of the larger earth data science ecosystem and crafting the working definition of diversity for ESIL. To establish the needs within the community, the evaluators will conduct a needs assessment with the broader Earth Data Science community to inform the development of ESIL activities, tools, and offerings.

Input Evaluation: During the input evaluation, the evaluation team will collaboratively define the ESIL community and key partners in close collaboration with and with input from the leadership team, conduct a literature review of existing relevant research, assess existing materials, plans and documentation, and identify the overlap with the Team Science and the Diversity, Equity and Inclusion teams. The evaluation team will align the mission statement, values, and center goals with the evaluation activities collaboratively with the leadership team. The evaluation team will populate coordination documents for collaborative planning purposes and develop a timeline of activities and milestones in alignment with the available resources.

Process Evaluation: The process evaluation will focus on the formative evaluation of all activities being conducted as part of ESIL, such as the annual summit, the working groups, the ESIL stars program, the postdocs, and the hackathon. The process evaluation will assess the quality of all activities that are carried out or implemented and it will support iterative revisions and improvements of all activities and the overall program design.

Product Evaluation: The product evaluation is often known as summative evaluation. It will focus on the assessment of the intended and unintended outcomes and address the evaluation questions. The product evaluation will provide measurable impacts and outcomes, as well as generalizable findings.

Figure 3. CIPP evaluation components (drawing A. Hartwell).

The product evaluation will include data from the broader Earth Data science community and partners to broaden the view of the activities.

GUSKEY'S EVALUATION MODEL

The Guskey evaluation model was designed as a professional development evaluation model. The review-oriented model is based on the concept of “teacher change”, in which a teacher models their professional practice as part of a learning community of educators. This modeling of learning has been shown to be effective in changing teacher professional practice by contributing to and fostering learning and thus ultimately affecting student learning and impacts. Guskey’s framework builds on the assumption that once teachers experience a new teaching method or new content, this professional development will cause the teachers to modify their knowledge and beliefs, which then leads to change in their teaching and classroom practice. While the model is conceptualized as a linear, causal process in which each step leads to the next (Fig. 4), the accumulated process results in increased impact (Hanover Research, 2014; Guskey et al, 2014).

Figure 4. Guskey's five-level evaluation model assesses professional development programs and their outcomes.

The ESIL Stars program and data short course offerings will be evaluated using Guskey’s evaluation model. The model differentiates between the participants in the professional development and the students that are being taught by these instructors. The evaluation will include the following offerings:

Level 1 Participants’ Reactions: ESIL stars participants will provide feedback on the program offerings. They will be asked about their satisfaction, measures about their engagement and the usefulness of the programming.

Level 2 Participants’ Learning: ESIL stars participants’ knowledge and skill gains will be assessed, the quality of the learning and the outcomes such as attitudes, sense of belonging and confidence as well as overall feedback on the experience.

Level 3 Organization Support and Change: Evaluators will examine the broader context of the ESIL Stars program and the professional practice, the work environment, and the virtual context.

Level 4 Participants’ Use of New Knowledge and Skills: This level will assess the application of the learned skills or content in the ESIL Stars program, focusing on the internship program and the application of the skills and knowledge acquired. The evaluation will measure how effectively learners apply their knowledge and skills.

Level 5 Student Learning Outcomes: This final level will focus on the outcomes and impacts of the ESIL stars program on students and their learning.

ESIL Evaluation Focus

In applying the three evaluation frameworks, the evaluation activities will support the ESIL goals:

- 1. Evaluation to guide the center’s research agenda** – The evaluation team will conduct an initial needs assessment within the broader Earth Data science community and ESIL partners to support the development of the decadal research agenda and refine and guide the ESIL activities and priorities.
- 2. Evaluation to support the development of a large data center and a data user community** – Data will be collected to describe the development, successes, key components, and structures as the center develops and grows, in order to understand success factors that support the growth of centers and communities. The data collection will include network analyses as part of a large multi-year study.
- 3. Team Science Research** – ESIL’s Team Science group will study the interdisciplinary teams that are part of this synthesis center. Evaluation data will be collected to support this research, focusing on the ESIL leadership team as well as ESIL activities and collaborations (e.g., working groups, innovation summits).
- 4. Evaluation of the efficacy and improvement of the education programs** – Data will be collected from the participants of all educational programs (e.g., trainings, internships, workshops) to evaluate the efficacy of the programs and web-based offerings. Participants will be also enrolled in longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of their participation.
- 5. Evaluation of the diversity goals of the center** – Data will be collected on the effectiveness of the diversity initiatives within the center and the planned infusion of strong diversity, equity and inclusion norms and culture of inclusion guidelines within the transdisciplinary teams and the impacts these goals have on the center outcomes.
- 6. Evaluation of all program activities** – Evaluation data will be collected across all center activities, including both internal and external offerings and activities and longitudinal data. We will also collect impact measures such as web analytics and tracking. Evaluation data will be used to describe the overall impact of the ESIL center.
- 7. Leadership team evaluation** – The leadership team will be evaluated on a regular basis to provide an opportunity for reflection and common review and goal setting.

ESIL Project Goals & Logic Model

The high-level goals and the alignment with the activities and intended outcomes were initially summarized in the logic model originally written during the proposal stage of the ESIL project (See Table 2 and Figure 5.) In the following section, we include goals that were revised in collaboration with the evaluators through a series of leadership team meetings. Alignment with activities (table 2) will continue to be updated throughout the first year of ESIL

Figure 5. ESIL High-Level Center Goals from proposal.

Table 2. ESIL logic model from proposal.

High-Level Goals	Activities	Short-Term Outcomes	Long-Term Outcomes
Synthesis Center and Convergent Research on Emerging Environmental Data Science (§1)			
Establish a decadal research agenda for EDS	Summits and Working Groups (WGs)	Identify emergent areas to pursue and precipitate new insights & concepts through deep disciplinary integration	Solutions-oriented science that contributes to societal adaptation to global environmental change
Build leadership for culturally-relevant, solutions-based EDS as an incubator for open science through inclusion of diverse perspectives and democratized access	ESIL Training series	Participants feel equipped to contribute to EDS	Diverse participants actively contribute to team science
	ESIL Postdoc Cohort	Post-Docs publish manuscripts on emergent EDS themes	Postdocs graduate into EDS jobs related to the work they published
Team Science: Diversity & Culture of Inclusion (§2)			
Facilitate effective ESIL WGs	Employ best practices in supporting ESIL WGs based on past research on synthesis teams	ESIL WGs have the resources and support to be maximally effective	EDS science community effectively participates in team science and collaboration
Increase understanding of creativity, productivity, and policy impacts in scientific teams	Conduct social science research on ESIL Incubator WG dynamics and their scientific and policy outcomes	Conference presentations and publication of academic articles in scholarly journals	Enhanced ability to promote effective team science in EDS research and other specialties in the future
Education, Training, and Diversity (§5)			
Increase diverse participation in EDS career pathways	Host ESIL Stars Program: student participation from MSIs in project-based learning, synergistic with Earth Data Science Corps	Students feel supported in their hands-on projects	Students pursue degrees in STEM
			Students are confident to find answers to EDS questions
Build capacity for EDS teaching and research	Host ESIL Data Short Course: teaches core data and analytics skills and builds EDS career awareness	Students feel excited and encouraged to apply their skills in future endeavors	Students continue learning EDS and use it regularly
Make EDS education universally accessible (open education)	Host ESIL Data Short Course online for asynchronous, open access	Global online and downloadable access to lessons and curricula available to 200,000+ unique users/month via EarthDataScience.org	Thousands of additional users per month with growth associated with ESIL WG deliverables
	Develop Interactive Online Analytics textbook developed with culturally-relevant modules		
Cyberinfrastructure and Data Analytics Tools (§6)			
Enable seamless User Experience (UX) from freeware to open, scalable cyberinfrastructure for big data analysis on the cloud	Develop CASE driven by community needs leveraging Cyverse, XSEDE, Cloudbank, and ImgSPEC	ESIL Students transition smoothly to using ESIL CASE	ESIL Students use CASE for big data analytics and research
	Integrate data APIs into CASE User Interface for easy access	ESIL Network subset big data to data needed for analysis	ESIL Network regularly rely on big data for their analyses
	Provide API and Workflow User Guides		
Reduce barriers for shared, collaborative data tools to streamline data munging and enable novel data analytics that accelerate scientific advancement	Develop common Data Tools from WGs	From WGs, create software packages to curate data and workflows to analyze	Researchers use and cite software and workflows from others
	Host hackathons to solve common challenges found by Summits	Identify novel data analytics for Env. Sci. challenges	Integrate identified analytics into WG workflows
	Embed Data Analytics expertise in WGs	Env. scientists use novel data analytics in manuscripts	Env. scientists partner with data scientists on proposals

ESiIL Goals & Evaluation Questions

Guided by the three evaluation frameworks, the high-level ESiIL program goals for each of the main focus areas within ESiIL were refined and updated from the initial draft in the proposal (table 2) in close collaboration with the ESiIL leadership team during the first few months of the project. Through a series of discussions and with extensive input from the leadership and subgroup teams, we then developed guiding evaluation questions for each area of focus within the ESiIL synthesis center that align with the ESiIL goals. A summary of this alignment matrix is shown in table 3 but may be found in the online ESiIL [Evaluation Question Matrix](#).

High-Level Goals: Collaborative Team and Leadership Evaluation		
Engage ESiIL Team and Advisory Board members in a collaborative evaluation of their processes, progress toward center goals, and success in fostering a culture of inclusion, including learning within the leadership team.	Engage ESiIL subteams in a collaborative evaluation of processes, progress toward subteam goals, and success in fostering a culture of inclusion.	Provide formative and summative evaluations with ESiIL programs and activity participants toward understanding impacts on Diversity and a Culture of Inclusion

Evaluation Questions

- In which ways has a culture of inclusion been implemented within the ESiIL team and across the center?
- Which approaches have been effective for the ESiIL leadership team in working together towards the common goals of the center?
- What challenges has the ESiIL leadership team experienced and how have they addressed those challenges?
- How does the ESiIL leadership team foster leadership in working groups and during other ESiIL offerings?

High-Level Goals: Convergent Research on Environmental Data Science		
Establish a decadal research agenda for EDS	Establish ESiIL as an incubator for open science, prioritizing the inclusion of diverse perspectives and democratized access.	Impact policy development and industry applications to support and foster the use of Environmental Data Science

Evaluation Questions

- To what extent has ESiIL coordinated the development, broad dissemination and implementation of a decadal research agenda driven by community interest, community needs, and societal needs?
- In which ways has ESiIL included diverse perspectives (including transdisciplinary perspectives) in EDS activities and products?
- In which ways has ESiIL included democratized access to EDS resources and offerings?
- In which ways has ESiIL contributed to culturally relevant and solutions-oriented open earth data science?
- How has the ESiIL community evolved over the course of the grant period (e.g., demographically, in data skills, in capacity to work across inter-trans-disciplinary teams, depth of their engagement)?
- In what ways has ESiIL precipitated discoveries?
- How has ESiIL grown the EDS community and expanded its connections (e.g., through building connections between fields and existing networks and bringing in new people and organizations)?

High-Level Goals: Team Science

Facilitate effective collaborations across all ESIL activities (e.g., Working Groups, Summit, Hackathon)

Increase understanding of creativity, productivity, and policy impacts in scientific teams

Evaluation Questions:

- To what extent have ESIL activities/collaborations been incubators of innovation, discovery, creativity, and productivity?
- How does diversity affect ESIL collaborations (e.g., working groups, summit, hackathon) dynamics?
- In which ways have the team science research methods grown an understanding of effective ESIL collaboration practices and outcomes?
- To what extent have participants in ESIL activities/collaborations engaged with policy, policymakers, or industry?

High-Level Goals: Education, Training, and Diversity

Increase diverse participation in EDS career pathways

Build capacity for EDS teaching and research

Make EDS education universally accessible (open education)

Evaluation Questions:

- To what extent has participation in ESIL activities (e.g., Stars Program, Hackathon, Summit, Postdocs) changed EDS community members' sense of belonging and data science identity?
- To what extent has participation in ESIL educational activities (e.g., Stars Program, Postdocs) changed EDS community members' career paths?
- How successful have the dissemination efforts been for EDS education materials?
- To what extent has the Stars program been able to increase capacity for EDS teaching and research?

High-Level Goals: Cyber Infrastructure and Data Analytics Tools

Enable use of cloud-native workflows and seamless User Experience (UX) from freeware to open, scalable cyberinfrastructure for big data analysis on the cloud

Reduce barriers for shared, collaborative data tools to streamline data munging and enable novel data analytics that accelerates scientific advancement

Support users that span gradients of experience (skills), domain of expertise, identity, access, and security

Evaluation Questions

- To what extent do the CI and Data Analytics tools meet the needs of users?
- How widely are the CI and Data Analytics tools being used?
- In which ways has ESIL effectively reduced barriers for CI and Data Analytics tools towards an accelerated scientific achievement?
- In which ways does Cyberinfrastructure generate more inclusion of diverse people across experience, domain of expertise, identity, access, and security?
- In which ways does CI support convergent research and discovery?
- How does CI facilitate the use of cloud-native workflows and seamless user experiences?

High-Level Goals: Diversity, Culture of Inclusion

Support diverse voices and participation in the leadership and overall activities of the center.

Build and maintain a sense of belonging and inclusion for all participants in ESIL

Build capacity for diverse and inclusive leadership in EDS.

Evaluation Questions:

- To what extent has the center included diverse voices and partners and encouraged the participation of diverse groups, including groups that have historically not been part of EDS?
- In which ways is a culture of inclusion implemented and fostered across the center?
- How do participants experience the culture of inclusion at ESIL?
- How does ESIL foster a sense of belonging among EDS community members?
- In which ways have participants' involvement in and leadership of activities in ESIL activities evolved over time?

Evaluation Plan

Evaluation Activities

The evaluation team will engage in collaborative evaluation with the ESIIIL leadership team and advisory board to support progress toward center goals and success in fostering a culture of inclusion. The evaluation team will also conduct formative and summative evaluation for all ESIIIL activities and collaborations as well as ESIIIL educational and training programs as described below:

ESIIIL CENTER

Evaluation in this area will focus on documenting the development of ESIIIL over time and support success in addressing high-level center goals around establishing a decadal research agenda for EDS; promoting inclusion of diverse perspectives in EDS and open science.

- Formative evaluation on all events, workshops, webinars to facilitate iterative improvements
- Use, accessibility, and reach of EDS resources through web analytics
- Tracking: Using data collected via surveys, participant database with demographic information, and web analytics, we will track the following:
 - Products and innovations (e.g., publications, presentations, and other relevant products of ESIIIL collaborations)
 - Indicators towards goals
 - Demographic information for participants in ESIIIL educational and training programs as well as events and collaborations (e.g., Summit, Hackathon; Working Groups)

ESIIIL LEADERSHIP TEAM & ADVISORY BOARD Evaluation Activities

- ESIIIL Team and Advisory Board Reflections: The evaluation team will meet with ESIIIL leadership team members and advisory board members periodically (e.g., every 6 months or annually) to engage in reflection on how the team is working together and the progress of the data center. The format will include elements of a “Rose, Bud, Thorn” protocol in which team members reflect on positive experiences or areas of success (Rose), challenges that need to be addressed (Thorn), and hopes for future growth and improvement (Bud).
- Advisory Board Surveys: The evaluation team will invite advisory board member to participate in a brief formative survey after regular advisory board meetings to help with iterative improvement of communication and processes involved in collaborations and contributions of the advisory board.

ESIIIL Community Evaluation Activities

- Initial Needs Assessment: The evaluation team will engage the leadership team in a survey and listening session to gather perspectives on the needs of the EDS community, target strategies and prioritize activities toward establishing the center and meeting ESIIIL’s high-level goals. This will inform further data collection with the larger EDS community.
- EDS Community Needs Assessment: The evaluation team will survey members of the broader EDS community to identify needs, barriers or challenges, and areas for growth toward building an inclusive EDS community and for fostering data science and synthesis through the ESIIIL data center.
- Social Network Analysis: A survey will be shared with attendees at the annual Innovation Summit events, to track connections within and across the Environmental Data Science Community and establish an understanding of the development and growth of the ESIIIL community.
- Demographic information: Demographic information on participants in ESIIIL activities and collaborations will be gathered in a central database and tracked across all activities that participants will participate in to avoid having to repeatedly ask demographic questions.

WORKING GROUP Evaluation Activities

- Formative Evaluation survey: ongoing formative evaluation on working group progress and challenges will be conducted through a brief survey regularly (e.g., monthly, quarterly, depending on WG scheduling). Summarized and de-identified feedback will be reported back to the group and the ESIL leadership team to inform continual improvement.
- Pre- and Post-Surveys: Working group members will take a baseline pre-survey, and annually a post-survey to gather feedback on the effectiveness of collaborative work, ESIL's culture of inclusion, and to track products and innovations resulting from the collaboration.
- Interviews/Focus Groups: working group members will be invited to participate in an interview or focus group discussion with the evaluation team annually in addition to the post-survey as a deep listening activity to gather in-depth feedback on the working groups' progress and challenges.

Note: All evaluation activities of the WGs will be designed in close collaboration with ESIL's Team Science team to avoid duplication of data collection.

POSTDOC Evaluation Activities

- Baseline Evaluation: The evaluation team will collect data through a short baseline survey for all new postdocs to learn about their experience within EDS, their professional development interest and needs and suggestions on how to best support the postdoc cohort.
- Formative Evaluation Survey/Focus Group: Annually, the postdocs will be asked to reflect on their experience within the ESIL synthesis center. The data will be collected either through a survey or a focus group, depending on the timing of the establishment of the postdoc cohort. This data will inform the ESIL leadership team on how to iteratively improve the postdoc experience and support within the ESIL synthesis center.
- Summative Evaluation Survey or Exit Interview: A summative survey or exit interview will gather data from each postdoc on their overall experience, their professional growth and on the culture within the cohort, looking for indicators that foster innovation and transdisciplinary cutting edge synthesis science and overall data on the quality of the opportunities and trainings that were offered to the postdocs.
- Tracking: The career trajectories of each postdoc will be tracked through an annual career survey to collect longitudinal data.

INNOVATION SUMMIT & HACKATHON Evaluation Activities

- Baseline Evaluation: The evaluation team will develop a short survey as part of the annual Innovation Summit and the Hackathon registration to learn about experience, expectations and ideas to inform the development of the summit/hackathon offerings.
- Formative Evaluation Survey: Formative feedback on processes, positive experiences, and challenges will be gathered via survey at the annual Innovation Summit and the Hackathon events to inform iterative improvement of these events for members of the ESIL/EDS community.
- Summative Evaluation Survey: A summative survey will gather data from attendees of the Innovation Summit events to gather feedback on the effectiveness of the unconference style format and the collaborative work within ESIL, ESIL's culture of inclusion, and to track products and innovations generated by ESIL/EDS community members.
- Social Network Analysis: A survey will be shared with attendees at Innovation Summit events annually, to track connections within and across the ESIL/EDS Community (see also above).

ESIL CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE INTEGRATION Activities and Tools

- Web Analytics: Web analytics will be used to track the use of CI data tools to measure their impact, reach and accessibility.
- CI Data Tools user surveys: Brief, pop-up surveys will be embedded in the access portals for CI data tools to evaluate the extent to which the tools are meeting the needs of users.
- Summative Evaluation Survey: The summative evaluation survey shared annually with innovation summit attendees will include questions to assess the use and accessibility of CI data tools.

ESII EDUCATION Evaluation Activities

Evaluation in this area will assess the impact of the ESII STARS program, the Data Short Course and the Open Access Online Analytics Textbooks. The use of online resources will be collected using web analytics.

ESII Stars Program will be modeled after the EDSC evaluation and include:

- Pre-Program Participant survey: Data will be collected about participants level of experience with data science, their sense of belonging and science identity and expectations for the program.
- Mid-Program reflection surveys: Formative feedback will be collected to inform the ESII Stars instructors on ways to improve the program experience. Data will be collected from students and mentors.
- Post-Program Reflection survey: Data will be collected on participant learning and comfort with earth data science and around computing skills, their sense of belonging and science interest, their reflection on the program offerings and measure the program's impact and participant learning.
- Skill Assessment: A data skill assessment will be conducted at the end of the program where each student will receive a data analysis prompt and their approach and ability to complete the data analysis tasks will provide information on their skill development.
- Reflection focus groups: Additional data will be gathered in participant focus groups or interviews on the overall experience with the program.
- Longitudinal tracking: Program participants will be tracked in their career trajectory and asked annually to share their current position and the ways in which they apply earth data science.

ESII data short course:

- Pre-course registration survey: A registration survey will inform the course instructors about participants experiences and expectations for the workshop.
- Post-course survey: Data will be collected on participant learning in a variety of categories using retrospective techniques to assess self-perceived gains and impact of the program. Data will also be collected on career plans or application of EDS skills and overall reflection of the course.

Methodology

Design and Instrumentation

The evaluation team will use a mixed-method approach with quantitative and qualitative data collection. Year 1 will focus on collecting baseline data and more exploratory evaluation to understand the community and the EDS landscape and testing and refining of evaluation instruments. It will also include periodic, formative evaluation with ESII activity participants and collaboration groups (e.g., working groups; hackathon participants; education and training participants). Quantitative data will be collected through Likert scale data and also include tracking of web analytics on the access and use of ESII open-source tools and data; products and innovations derived from ESII activities and collaborations; and numbers of participants at each ESII activity or collaboration and at training events. Qualitative data will include open-ended survey responses and transcriptions of interviews, focus groups, and listening sessions; as well as data gathered using online or in-person discussion or collaborative data collection tools (e.g., Google Jamboard; Zoom whiteboard; hand-written responses on chart paper or dry erase board).

A Social Network Analysis will also be conducted each year at the annual ESIL Innovation Summit. The evaluation team will invite summit participants to complete network survey questions included within the larger evaluation survey for the summit and assess social network connections along different dimensions and assess a variety of attributes that will help describe and explore the network structure. The Summit participants will represent the people and organizations that are actively engaged with ESIL. Comparison between annual surveys of social network metrics will allow describing the evolution of the community.

All survey data will be collected using Qualtrics online surveys. Surveys will be disseminated via email or QR codes that can be scanned with a mobile device during in-person events. Focus groups, interviews, and listening sessions will be audio recorded and transcribed with the permission of participants. We will create a database for all ESIL participants with their demographic information and a tracking code. That will allow us to not ask demographic questions multiple times.

Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Protocols for data collection will be submitted to the University of Colorado Boulder IRB to obtain approval for data collection and analysis for each area of focus in the evaluation (e.g., needs assessment; social network analysis; evaluation with education and training groups). Data collection, storage, and analysis procedures will follow the guidelines for conducting human research and evaluation at CU. Data will be kept confidential. In many contexts, evaluation feedback will be gathered anonymously without identifying information for the participants. In contexts where it is necessary to record names or personally identifiable information, the data will be de-identified using an identification code.

Analysis and Interpretation Plan

[Will be developed once all instruments are *developed*]

Use, Dissemination and Sharing Plan

The evaluation team will regularly provide reports of evaluation findings to the ESIL leadership team. The evaluators will share a written report of evaluation findings after each ESIL event. The evaluation team will participate in ESIL leadership meetings and initiate discussions about evaluation findings or request input or collaborative development of evaluation plans, through written feedback or team discussions. Evaluation findings will be shared and discussed with the Team Science and the Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Teams on a regular basis in subteam meetings.

At the end of each year, the evaluation team will compile and synthesize findings in an annual evaluation report. This report will include a section that tracks ESIL's progress toward its goals and a summary of key findings and recommendations.

A comprehensive summative evaluation report will be completed at the end of the program duration after 5 years.

Timeline

The evaluation activities will match the overall ESIL activities as outlined in figure 6. Table 4 shows the evaluation activities in more detail for year 1, the evaluation timeline can also be viewed [here](#). An updated timeline will be shared with the ESIL leadership team annually and align with the ESSIL activities.

Figure 6. ESIL timeline of activities and milestones from the proposal.

Table 4. ESIL evaluation activities for year 1.

Evaluation Activities	Quarter 1			Quarter 2			Quarter 3			Quarter 4		
	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
Evaluation Plan & Evaluation Activity Development	IRB determination	ESIL kick-off meeting	Evaluation Plan Development with Evaluation Team	Evaluation Plan Development w/ESIL Leadership Team (alignment of Goals and Evaluation questions); Development of Leadership Needs Assessment Survey	Evaluation Plan Development w/ESIL Leadership Team	Share Evaluation Plan document with ESIL leadership team	Collaborative Development of Year 1 Evaluation instruments					
ESIL Needs Assessment				IRB development	Send out Leadership Needs Assessment survey	Listening session with ESIL Leadership Team	Send out Community Needs Assessment Survey & conduct Listening Sessions	Needs Assessment Analysis & reporting				
Social Network Analysis									IRB development		SNA data collection, analysis and reporting	
Working Groups (WGs) Evaluation							IRB development & approval	Working group evaluation (baseline)			WG evaluation (survey, focus group)	Evaluation report on WGs
Innovation Summit Evaluation									IRB development		Summit evaluation data collection, analysis and reporting	
Hackathon Evaluation												IRB, development
Postdoc Cohort Evaluation								IRB development	Postdoc evaluation (baseline)			
ESIL Stars Evaluation								IRB development	Pre-program survey			Retrospective post-training survey
Advisory Board Evaluation							IRB development	AB evaluation (baseline)				
CI and Data Infrastructure, Tools Evaluation							Partnering on CI needs assessment development					Develop CI evaluation plan
Collaborative evaluation with ESIL Project teams							Retreat evaluation	6-month check-in reflections with ESIL Teams		Reporting on Team check-ins		
Tracking (outcomes, webanalytics)						Develop plan for tracking	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing

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